

ARTISTIC AND AESTHETIC CHARACTERISTICS OF MUSICAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: This article discusses the artistic-aesthetic features of activities in music culture classes of general secondary education.

Key words: Music activities, music literacy, vocal performance, listening to music, interval, composer's creativity.

The art of music has a strong emotional impact on the young generation, and requires not only active and deep perception of it, but also the formation and development of independent knowledge about this art. From the first year of education, musical activities are carried out with children in class. Therefore, to achieve that they have special ideas about the musical activities carried out in the lesson, that is, listening to music, reading music, singing, musical rhythmic movements, getting to know the sounds of instruments, getting to know the work of artists, etc. necessary. In order for the above-mentioned musical elements to be performed consciously, voluntarily and with pleasure, it is important to have interest and needs in musical activities.

Musical activities:

- ❖ *Music literacy*
- ❖ *Singing;*
- ❖ *listening to music;*
- ❖ *music literacy;*
- ❖ *playing on children's musical instruments.*¹

Despite this, the aspect of the music lesson that differs from other subjects in the school is practical activity, i.e. implementation of executive activity, organization of the artistic process.

The organization of this artistic process has its own characteristics.

- *In order to perform singing or listening activities, it is necessary to have a comfortable mental and emotional environment, a comfortable situation in the group of students.*
- *children should be prepared in advance for singing or listening activities, they should have an appropriate mood and mental state.*
- *It is desirable that the sung work should be interesting to some extent for children.*
- *it is important for the music teacher to have the skills to convey this work to children, to be able to interest them in the activity of singing.*

¹ Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.

Also, the existing musical abilities of students play an important role in ensuring the success of singing activities.

Abilities are such individual mental characteristics of a person that the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities depends on the level of abilities. But these features themselves do not depend on knowledge, skills, and qualifications. Abilities are manifested in the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities. Ability is the basis for qualifications, skills and knowledge. It is based on opportunity and ability. Since human ability is an opportunity for knowledge, skills and abilities, the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities based on this opportunity depends on many things, including the effectiveness of educational organization and certain environmental conditions.

Musical abilities consist of opportunities for musical activity, and for their development and improvement, internal and external conditions are needed, which is manifested only in musical activity itself. It is known that intellectual development takes place in the process of education. Now a child who cannot solve a problem independently solves it with the help of adults. After gaining experience, he learns to do it independently. That's why researchers recommend to study it at least three times to determine human ability. The first task is solved independently, the second time it is solved with the help of an adult, and the third time it is performed independently with correction and understanding.

In particular, it is desirable to determine the musical ability of the child by comparing the results of the study at least three times. If the quality change in the child is the same in all three cases, it can be concluded that the child's ability is not high.

Voice capabilities of students are important in performing singing activities. Also, in this activity, it is necessary to have collective activity, that is, the need to sing, and the desire of children to listen to each other and perform the activity.

It is important for students to have musical auditory imagination, the need to listen, and interest in listening to certain genres of music.

In addition, it is desirable to have the need to listen to multi-voiced music, the ability to listen to harmonics, while listening to different musical works, genres, directions, ensembles and orchestras of different compositions, distinguishing them.

The activities of musical literacy mainly consist of learning the theoretical aspects of music, the expression of musical tones in musical notation, modes, tonalities, intervals, sound extension, repetition of a certain part of a piece of music.

By classes, the following situation is observed in primary classes:

In the first grade, singing of vowels and consonants, getting to know national instruments, saying the name of sounds to the right and left, high and soft, strong and thick sounds, ensemble, orchestra, soloist, left key, composer, poet, musician and singer, length and shortness of sounds, placement of notes on the musical score, national musical notes, quarter, semi-quarter, half and whole notes, rebus-games on identifying notes, composers M. Burhonov, F. Nazarov, Yunus Rajabi, G'. Kadirov, M. Mirzaev, as well as riddles on finding the names of notes.

In the second class, musical notation, counting them, quarter and half-quarter pauses, beat, beat line, instrumental notes, composers Il.Akbarov, SH.Yormatov, A.Mansurov, N.Norho'jaev, D.Omonullaeva, M. Glinka, major and minor, conducting exercises, return sign, melody and its structure are analyzed.

In the third class, composers R.Abdullaev, F.Alimov, H.Rahimov, L.Mujdaboeva, P.Chaykovskiy, exercises of conducting movements, quarter and half-quarter pauses, choral work and ensemble, orchestra, major and minor, sixteenth note, triad.²

In the fourth grade - scales, song genre, C major chord, alteration signs, national instrument lyrics, photos of famous musicians, composers T. Jalilov, I. Ikromov, K. Jabborov, F. Sodikov, I say, pause, rest and percussion instruments, minor scale, circle instrument, alla, 6/8 measure, singing exercises are presented.

The following scenario is observed according to secondary school textbooks:

In the fifth grade - properties of noisy and musical sounds, orchestra and its types, materials about noisy and musical sounds, keys in music, notation and their writing, sound lines and octaves, tones and semitones, signs of alteration in music, scores and pianos, in music dynamic markings, bar extension marks, pauses in music, concept of intervals, return and punctuation marks in music, cantatas and oratorios, rhythm (method), beat and bar line, measures in music, breaking notes into beats Conducting, conducting, 2/4, 3/4, and 4/4 time signatures.

In the sixth grade, singing is performed under the guidance of a conductor of exercises of different tonality, measure and character.

In the seventh grade - to strengthen knowledge about intervals, pauses, tonic, semitone and whole tone, major tone, natural minor, method, singers M. SHerozi, J. Sulstonov, composers Yu. Rajabi, Shoberdi Bakshi Boltaev, Haji Abdulaziz Rasulov, Bolabakhshi Abdullaev, Fazil Yoldosh ogle, tanburchi T.Alimatov, kashkarcha method, buzruk status vowel, true status vowel, ufor, dugoh vowel, segoh vowel, iraq vowel, strengthening knowledge about intervals, strengthening knowledge about methods, natural major scale (sound), natural minor scale (sound), dynamic signs, materials such as strengthening knowledge about ufar are presented.

In conclusion, it can be said that the materials intended for all musical activities in the school music textbooks are placed in a certain consistency and in a logical way, and in order to fully convey these materials to the students and to form their interest in these activities, music education is necessary. A great pedagogical task lies before the teacher. Complete fulfillment of this task is important for the formation of students as perfect human beings.

² Kharatova, S. K. (2022). Characteristics of the pedagogical process system. *Science and Education*, 3(6), 681-686.

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